

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN THE SOCIETY AND THEIR GENDER EQUALITY

Umarova Feruza Nigmatovna¹, Azizova Makhsuda Ahmadaliyevna², Kholmurodova Ezoza Xasanovna³, Teshaeva Dildora O‘tkir qizi⁴

^{1,2,3}Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers, National Research University Senior teachers of English department, ⁴Assistant teacher

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Abstract. Gender is the term used to describe socially constructed categories based on sex (sex refers to a biological distinction). Gender is a social construction. It passes through the concept of gender that society transforms female and male human beings into social women and men, assigning their roles and giving them cultural value. Women in recent years have been given an equal opportunity as men to participate in some areas such as politics, education. Gender equality is achieved when women and men enjoy the same rights and opportunities across all sectors of society, including economic participation and decision-making, and when the different behaviors, aspirations and needs of women and men are equally valued and favored. Gender equality is not only a fundamental human right, but it is a necessary foundation for a peaceful, prosperous and sustainable world. The state of equal ease of access to resources and opportunities regardless of gender and the state of valuing different manners, and needs equally is discussed in this article.

Key words: gender, equality, concept of gender, cultural value, society, behaviors, opportunities, aspirations, economic participation.

Abstract. Gender - bu jinsga asoslangan ijtimoiy tuzilgan toifalarni tavsiflash uchun ishlatiladigan atama (jins biologik farqni bildiradi). Gender - bu ijtimoiy qurilish. Jamiyat ayol va erkak insonlarni ijtimoiy ayollar va erkaklarga aylantirib, ularning rollarini belgilash va ularga madaniy qadriyat berish gender tushunchasidan o'tadi. So'nggi yillarda ayollarga siyosat, ta'lim kabi ba'zi sohalarida qatnashish uchun erkaklar bilan teng imkoniyat berildi. Gender tengligiga ayollar va erkaklar jamiyatning barcha sohalarida, jumladan, iqtisodiy ishtirok etish va qarorlar qabul qilishda bir xil huquq va imkoniyatlarga ega bo'lganda, ayollar va erkaklarning turli xulq-atvori, intilishlari va ehtiyojlari bir xilda qadrlansa va qo'llab-quvvatlansa erishiladi. Gender tengligi nafaqat insonning asosiy huquqi, balki tinch, farovon va barqaror dunyo uchun zarur asosdir. Jinsdan qat'i nazar, resurslar va imkoniyatlardan foydalanishning teng qulayligi holati va turli xil odatlar va ehtiyojlarni teng darajada baholash holati ushbu maqolada muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: gender, tenglik, gender tushunchasi, madaniy qadriyat, jamiyat, xatti-harakatlar, imkoniyatlar, intilishlar, iqtisodiy ishtirok.

Аннотация. Гендер — это термин, используемый для описания социально сконструированных категорий, основанных на поле (пол относится к биологическому различию). Гендер — это социальная конструкция. Она проходит через концепцию гендера, в которой общество трансформирует женщин и мужчин в социальных женщин и мужчин, назначая им роли и придавая им культурную ценность. В последние годы женщинам были предоставлены равные возможности с мужчинами для участия в некоторых областях, таких как политика, образование. Гендерное равенство

достигается, когда женщины и мужчины пользуются одинаковыми правами и возможностями во всех секторах общества, включая экономическое участие и принятие решений, и когда различное поведение, стремления и потребности женщин и мужчин одинаково ценятся и поддерживаются. Гендерное равенство — это не только одно из основных прав человека, но и необходимая основа для мирного, процветающего и устойчивого мира. В этой статье обсуждается состояние равной легкости доступа к ресурсам и возможностям независимо от пола и состояние равной оценки различных манер и потребностей.

***Ключевые слова:** гендер, равенство, концепция гендера, культурная ценность, общество, поведение, возможности, стремления, экономическое участие.*

Introduction. Gender stereotypes are structured beliefs about the socio-psychological characters of women believe that men and women are substantially different on number characteristics [1]. I prefer to think that all people are the same no matter what you are – a man or a woman. We all eat, drink, sleep, cough, and laugh at the same things. But in some ways each person is different and individuals’ differing wants and preferences may conflict with each other. Many conflicts between men and women had happened in the world to prove who is better and supreme. Psychologists maintain that gender turns out to be the one of the most important determinants of human behavior, and try to make sense of seemingly senseless misunderstandings that haunt men and women relationships. Psychologists’ data show: women tend to focus of intimacy and men on independence. Though all humans need both intimacy and independence, women tend to focus on the first and men on the second. That is the main difference leading to numerous conflicts and problems between genders [2].

Research Methodology. About half of our population is women, so, democratically speaking; they deserve all the rights and importance in society, which can help them to perform their roles. Social norms construct and reinforce attitudes about women and men proper work roles, their participation in family and community life, modes of dress and demeanour and their appropriate styles of verbal behavior. That is a stereotype that a woman is a housewife and a man is a money-earner. People believe that men and women are substantially different on a number of characteristics. Men are considered higher in self-interest, women are considered higher in a concern of others. Men are forceful, adventurous, aggressive, self-confident, rude, independent, ambitious, active and dominant. Women are affectionate, emotional, gentle, weak, sensitive, nagging and sentimental.

Women are as important as men in any society. They stay in the house and keep it in good order. They cook food for the family. After marriage, they give birth to children. They provide every comfort to their husbands and children. Quite a few women stay outside the house to teach or work in government and private offices, hospitals, business centers, banks, and public places. In the villages, they work side by side with men in the fields and look after animals at home. In this way, they contribute to social and national progress.

The work and functions of women are greatly important for the family. Properly educated and trained women can be of immense help to their husbands and working members of the family. They can teach, train and bring up their children on the right lines. They can advise their husbands and other members of the family in important property, business and professional matters. Their role, then, in the family becomes supremely important [10].

We need educated and well-trained women in the villages and small towns. Female teachers, doctors, social workers, government officers, and teachers are needed everywhere. Many of our schools and colleges for girls are without enough female teachers. The clinics and hospitals in the villages and towns require female doctors, nurses and paramedics (doctors' helpers) in most places. Social workers for the guidance of women and children in the village and town streets, houses, markets and public places like parks, railway and bus stations, and health centers are urgently needed. These trained social workers can advise women and children about what they can and should do for a better life. They can tell them about safe and cheap travel from one place to another. They can discuss ways of keeping healthy and fit.

Results and Discussion. In the bigger cities, we need educated and trained women to work in schools, colleges and universities, hospitals, offices, firms and companies, airports and seaports, business centers, factories, TV stations, and newspaper offices in different capacities. The fields of engineering, aviation (flying and airplane operation), agriculture and industry are open to women now. They can work in the home and work outside to earn money and to keep active in professions of their liking. There are professions like medicine and teaching where women can work better than or equally well with men. Female schoolteachers, doctors, nurses, composers, artists, designers and shop assistants are in great demand. It all shows the importance and usefulness of women in our society and other societies as well.

For centuries, men considered women the less intelligent of the sexes. This terribly wrong perception caused immense loss to their self-dignity. However, at present, women have been playing major roles in politics, economy, household, society, and nation building. A youthful, fashion-conscious and smart girl has replaced the timid female of the past. Women are jostling shoulders with men and competing with them in engineering, sciences, space research, medicine, and business. This marked change in their status reflects the fact that their emancipation is almost complete.

Only, a few decades ago, the condition of the woman was increasingly poor. Her position was secluded and she was assigned a lower status in society. She was virtually condemned to lead her life as a beast of burden. For a very long time, she was unable to raise her status from a mere household drudge. She was forced to run the house and do all its furnishing, cleaning, cooking, sewing, sweeping, dusting, washing and so on. Besides this, she had to rear her children and serve her husband. She had to be respectful and submissive before men. They were denied all sort of higher education and were strictly confined to the four walls of the house. She was always treated in a brutal manner and was generally regarded as the silly, sentimental and dull creature. It was a common belief that women were created only to please men.

Women have finally come out of the four walls of the house and found their way to the higher educational institutions. Moreover, education, in turn, has enlightened them broadening their outlook and horizon simultaneously. They have set up their own organization for the welfare and progress of women at large. They have started claiming equal rights with men and have succeeded appreciably on many fronts. They have entered practical life and are playing a significant role for both their country and family. It is observed in recent times that a number of women are entering the once male-dominated management areas. They are taking an active part in the politics of the country and are fully determined to compete against men in every professional occupation [5].

Modern women are no longer ignorant and shy as women had been up to the near past. Now they are considerably brave and have a lot of confidence to accomplish the tasks assigned

to them. She has the complete liberty to decide her affairs quite independently. Man no more enjoys the right to impose his authority on women. She has virtually emerged as an earning member of the family, for today, men and women have to be the joint operators of the economic switchboard.

Today the world has undergone a sea change. The new economic affairs have impelled women to come out of their homes and join various professions in order to supplement the income of their menfolk. However, women, by nature, are tender, compassionate and sympathetic. They can, therefore, become good teachers, nurses, physicians, social workers, journalists, wardens of orphanages and homes for old and poor persons. This is, however, not to say that they cannot succeed in other professions. Some people object to nursing as something anti-Islamic. They are totally mistaken, for the pages of history give a vivid account of the brave Muslim women who helped the wounded Muslim warriors in the battlefields. The dramatic spread of education has enormously contributed to the positive approach of men towards women's careers. The medical field is regarded highly noble profession and woman doctors, as well as nurses, are respectable figures all over the country [6].

In modern times, almost all the professions are virtually open to women. They are entering public services as class I and class II officers in the executive Jobs as judicial magistrates, civil judges, income-tax officers, customs officers, school, college and university teachers and various other crucial jobs. Some women are joining as lawyers, secretaries, airhostesses, ticket collectors, computer operators, sales women, bank officers, and police officers and so on.

The women of the rural areas have always played an extremely active role in the economic field. They are no longer restricted to the fields only. They are working effectively in the fields of poultry breeding, sewing, embroidery, midwifery, nursing, preserving vegetables and fruits. The radio and television have made them fully aware of their rights. This development has changed the very face of the countryside regarding the status and dignity of women. Women should develop their aptitudes in accordance with their own nature without imitating the males. Their part in the progress of civilization is higher than that of men.

Women constitute nearly half the population of the East. The country where women are kept in ignorance is destined to be doomed. The history of the developed countries affords increasing evidence that the progress of a country has always synchronized with the liberation and education of women. The same thing happened in Japan and Turkey, and today we find that both the countries are counted among the developed countries of the world [7]. Matrimony is no more the sole aim of a woman's education; it has rather assumed new dimensions in recent times. Women are getting an education in order to perform well at home, at the workplace, in the community and society. So, much greater facilities are needed for the education and training of women at large.

Conclusion. Today's woman has decisively rejected the sentimental myth of "frailty which kept depicting her as man's plaything and a purchasable commodity. The woman is playing a crucially important role in the making of a nation. The man has also revised his attitude towards woman. *Ladies First* is the order of the day and the man calls it courtesy to conceal his defeat at the hands of a modern woman. Today's women are hardworking and sincere in all the occupations and are more productive than their male counterparts. To my mind, people downgrade women's achievements, sometimes they are great, people have negative opinions about women's work capacities though it is not always true; women have been represented

negatively in many areas though they work in most areas shoulder-to-shoulder with men; and women’s stereotypical characteristics are not as highly regarded as men’s are; though women are usually more tactful, punctual, responsible and hard-working than men [8].

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